

Wuzhen pian 悟真篇

also known as “Essay on the [Immediate] Awakening to Truth”, “Chapters on Awakening to Perfection”

By Wanmeng Li, UCLA

Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Scripture, Daoist text, Daoism, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

Wuzhen pian (DZ 263.26, j. 26-30 and DZ 1017, j. 18, “Essay on the [Immediate] Awakening to Truth.” Also translated as “Chapters on Awakening to Perfection.” Its preface is dated to 1075, and its postface is dated to 1078) is a seminal Daoist inner alchemical work that underpins inner alchemy as the essential method for immortal cultivation. Inner alchemy (neidan, which literally means internal cinnabar, 内丹) refers to a range of esoteric teachings and practices derived from diverse theories including but not limited to correlative cosmology, laboratory alchemy (also known as outer alchemy, waidan, 外丹) and the teachings of Yijing 易经 (Book of Changes). Unlike the laboratory alchemy practitioners, who aim to achieve immortality by consuming magical potions made of minerals and herbs, those who practice inner alchemy focus on meditation. In meditative practices, they visualize the human body as a cauldron that refines the internal vital forces including essence (jing 精), pneuma (qi 气), and spirit (shen 神) to produce an internal elixir, which will help them transcend. Wuzhen pian’s attributed author, Zhang Boduan 張伯端 (987?–1082), was worshipped as the founder of the Southern Lineage (Nanzong 南宗) of inner alchemy. The work was read as a commentary on the Zhouyi cantong qi 周易參同契 (Token for the Kinship of the Three According to the Zhouyi, DZ 999 and DZ 1004)—the earliest Chinese treatise on laboratory alchemy and granted equal importance in the teaching of inner alchemy. Most sections in Cantong qi were written as tetrasyllabic or pentasyllabic rhymed verses. A few other sections adopt the Sao style or prose style. Influenced by Cantong qi, Wuzhen pian also adopts the form of poetry. However, most sections in Wuzhen pian were septasyllabic quatrains or regulated verses, which are poetic forms that became dominant in the Tang dynasty (618–907). It also includes a section of song lyrics (ci 詞), a genre that became mainstream in the Song dynasty (906–1279). The Wuzhen pian’s adoption of the new poetic forms not only reveals the author’s mastery of poetry but also exemplifies the Daoist treatises’ achievement in introducing new contents to the literary tradition. The Wuzhen pian originally comprised eighty-one verses, which are divided into three sections: the first section consists of sixteen septasyllabic regulated verses that focus on the idea of “two times eight” mechanism, which embodies the dichotomy of yin and yang that functions with hexagrams; the second section includes sixty-four septasyllabic quatrains that incorporate the concept of the hexagram in the Book of Changes and the last pentasyllabic poem eulogizes the ideal of the Great Unity (taiyi 太一). Later, two additional sections were added: one section comprises twelve pieces of song lyrics following the tunes of Western River Moon (xijiangyue 西江月); the other contains thirty-two poems that elaborate on cultivation through Buddhist subjects. According to Zhang Boduan’s summary in the postface, the contents range from the teachings about “the ranking of vessels, the weight of medical ingredients, and the control of fire-phasing” to the method for distinguishing “the superiority and inferiority, existence and nonexistence, and auspicious and ominous.” The text’s highly esoteric and symbolic language indicates that oral instruction by a master was required during the learning process. Inevitably, its obscurity also led to various interpretations, stirring much debate among later commentators. While Wuzhen pian includes certain guidance for sexual techniques, commentators tended to disapprove of such contents. Instead, they emphasized the teaching of inner alchemy and the text’s relation to the Book of Changes. Two sets of Wuzhen pian’s inner alchemical concept were considered essential in later receptions. First, it inherited the theory of dual cultivation of nature and life (xingming shuangxiu 性命雙修) from the Zhong-Lü tradition, a Daoist meditative tradition that was active during the late Tang and regarded refining one’s nature (xing 性) and prolonging life (ming 命) as equally important. Second, it absorbs the theory refining essence, pneuma, and spirit, which was promoted by the Daoist master Chen Tuan’s 陳搏 (871–989), making these elements the key components for producing the internal cinnabar. Although the alleged author Zhang Boduan was active during the eleventh century, Wuzhen pian did not gain much attention until the mid-twelfth century. During the 1160s, many commentaries begin to appear, and the text itself becomes available in many editions. The edition that collects the earliest commentaries is a five juan version titled Wuzhen pian jizhu 悟真篇集註, which is mentioned in Zhizhai shulu jieti 直齋書錄解題, one of the most influential private book collection catalog composed by the Southern Song literatus Chen Zhensun 陳振孫 (1179–1262). Some major commentators and compilers include Weng Baoguang’s 翁葆光 (c. 12th century), Xia Yuanding 夏元鼎 (c. early 13th century), and Chen Zhixu 陳致虛 (b. 1290). The Taoist Canon: A Historical Companion to the Daozang edited by Kristofer Schipper and Franciscus Verellen provides a comprehensive list of Wuzhen pian editions and inspired works. About the later transmission of the treatise, the Wuzhen pian probably influenced the Northern Lineage of inner alchemy, which was represented by the Quanzhenjiao 全真教 (Teaching of Complete Perfection). Louis Komjathy argues that the Quanzhen tradition merged with the Southern Lineage on the eve of the fall of the Song dynasty. It is very likely that the Quanzhen tradition also engaged the inner alchemical theories established by Wuzhen pian.

Date Range: 1075 CE - 1078 CE

Region: Regions that potentially received the Wuzhen pian in the Song dynasty

Region tags: Asia, East Asia

The alleged first patriarch of the Southern lineage and the author of Wuzhen pian, Zhang Boduan, was first active in Zhejiang and then moved to Shaanxi and Sichuan regions. The second patriarch Shi Tai 石泰 (b.1022), moved from the Jiangnan region to Sichuan, where he received the teachings from Zhang Boduan and transmitted it to the third patriarch Xue Daoguang 薛道光 (1078–1191). Sichuan served as the center of the Wuzhen pian transmission until Bai Yuchan 白玉蟾 (1134–1229), the fifth patriarch who came from Hainan and was the de facto founder of the Southern Lineage, traveled around the country and brought the scripture to most regions ruled under the Southern Song government.

读者群情况：

✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

来源和语料库

纸质来源

用于理解此课题的纸质信息来源

—来源1: <https://book.douban.com/subject/26284512/>

—来源2: https://books.google.com/books?hl=zh-CN&lr=&id=OtLSYzjh8wMC&oi=fnd&pg=PR7&dq=Awakening+to+Reality%0AThe++Regulated+Verses++of+the+Wuzhen+pian,&ots=ODz_Pf2b6AAEfXtZLbv_0OnS9M#v=onepage&q&f=false

在线信息来源

用于理解此课题的在线信息来源

—来源1 URL: https://www.goldenelixir.com/jindan/wzp_index.html

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

在线语料库

相关在线一手文献语料库（原文以及/或者译文）

—来源1 URL: <https://zh.m.wikisource.org/zh-hant/%E6%82%9F%E7%9C%9F%E7%AF%87>

—来源1 描述: Wikisource entry

一般变量 (General Variables)

物质性 (Materiality)

创作方式

— 书写

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

书写/雕刻文字的媒介

— 纸

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况: 精英 宗教专家

↳ 请具体说明纸的类型

—请注明: paper used for manuscript copies or wood block printing

在书写和雕刻之前,材料是否被修改过?

—物质准备

在书写和雕刻之前,文本是否被修改过?

—其他【请注明】: Don't know

地点

文本是否存放于明确的场所?

【注明时间点,供参考(如果知道);选择所有适用答案。】

—是

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况: 精英 宗教专家

↳ 坟墓

—否

↳ 墓地

—否

↳ 寺庙

—是

Notes: The text entered Daozang, the copies of which were preserved in temples at different locations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况: 精英 宗教专家

↳ 神社

—是

↳ 神坛

—是

↳ 虔诚的记号

—否

↳ 纪念碑

—否

↳ 教堂

—否

↳ 清真寺
—否

↳ 犹太教堂
—否

↳ 凯旋门
—否

↳ 纪念碑
—否

↳ 大型聚集点
—否

↳ 洞穴
—未知领域

↳ 山顶
—否

↳ 其他自然避难所
—未知领域

↳ 边界标记或标记线
—否

↳ 家庭内环境 (domestic context)
—是

↳ 图书馆/档案馆
—是

Notes: The five juan Wuzhen pian jizhu is mentioned in Zhizhai shulu jieti, so one edition appeared in at least one private library. It was later collected by the imperial library.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况: ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 请注明

—请注明: There were probably also copies stored in literati studios.

存放文字的位置是否伴有标记或者图像？

—是

Notes: It is possible that the storage location kept iconography. Records reveal that certain versions of commentaries, for example, Ye Shibiao's 葉士表 work, are supplemented with illustrations. Additionally, some later texts inspired by Wuzhen pian also include images.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty
读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 标志或者意象出现在哪里？
选择所有适用答案
— 我不知道

↳ 有什么关于宗教团体标记或者形象特殊或者值得注意的特色或者属性？
— 未知领域

存放文字的区域是否有标志性的图像？
— 未知领域

生产和目标受众

生产

文本生产是否由政体资助？
— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Song Dynasty
读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

文本是否被认为是官方的宗教经文？
— 是

Notes: Wuzhen pian was an official scripture because it entered the Daoist Canon. It is unknown whether the Jin and Yuan dynasties' version of the Daoist Canon, Xuandu baozang 玄都寶藏, already included Wuzhen pian or not. However, the scripture likely entered the canon at least by the Yuan dynasty as the Quanzhen Daoism received it as an essential inner alchemy treatise. The Ming dynasty canon was compiled based on the remainder of the Yuan canon and included Wuzhen pian.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Song Dynasty
读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否有口头朗诵文化？
— 是

Notes: Wuzhen pian adopts the form of poetry, which indicates that it was meant for chanting and recitation.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Song Dynasty
读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否有与经文的起源有关的故事？
— 是

Specific to this answer:
Region: Northern Song Dynasty
读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由至上天神揭示？
— 否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由其他超自然存在揭示？

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 灵感来自至上天神？

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 灵感来自其他超自然存在？

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 源于神或半神的人类？

— 是

Notes: There are different narratives of the scripture's origin. One version tells that Zhang Boduan, the author of Wuzhen pian, studied with the perfected being Liu Haichan 劉海蟾 before he composed the scripture. Another account traced the transmission of the teaching to the deity Donghua shaoyang jun 東華少陽君. Wuzhenpian was also received as an elaboration of Wei Boyang's Zhouyi cantongqi. According to Ge Hong's 葛洪 Shenxian zhuan 神仙傳 (Traditions of Divine Transcendents), the first text that mentions Wei Boyang, Wei was from a prestigious family and transcended as an immortal. Zhang Boduan's identity is also controversial. Some sources refer to him as the perfected being (zhenren 真人). However, there are also texts that mention his death at the age of ninety-nine. It is likely that Zhang fabricated a mysterious origin for his scripture and was also deified in later receptions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 源自半神人类？

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 经文可以修改吗？

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否有正式的机构（即由宗教界或政治领袖授权的机构）来解释经文？

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否有一批经过训练的人传播经文？

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否有编辑成经典的经书？

— 是

Notes: The version of Wuzhen pian annotated by Weng Baoguang is collected in the Ming dynasty Daoist Canon. The Canon also includes some commentary works of Wuzhen pian. However, the treatise per se does not become a canon.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 能否更改或添加典籍？

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 附加评注是否属于目前理解的经典的一部分？

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

用特定的宗教/神圣的语言书写？

— 否

Notes: Still, the author chose to write in a poetic form, which distinguishes the treatise from other scriptures. Most sections in Wuzhen pian were septasyllabic quatrains or regulated verses, which are poetic forms that became dominant in the Tang dynasty (618–907). It also includes a section of song lyrics (ci 詞), a genre that became mainstream in the Song dynasty (906–1279).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

目标受众

估计有多少人被认为是文本的受众？

这应该是作为文本预期受众的总人数。

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教团体积极劝人信教、招募新成员吗？

—是

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 根据文本，劝人信教是必须的吗？

—否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 文中是否鼓励劝人信教？

—否

Notes: The author mentioned in the postface that the purpose of his composition was to use the text to disseminate his teaching.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 根据文本，有没有劝人信教的特别回报？

—否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 文本中是否接受强迫劝人信教？

—否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 在宗教团体中，劝教活动的文本理由是否属于规范？

—否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 文本是否对劝人信教之事保持沉默？

—是

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 即使文本中对劝教之事保持沉默，劝人信教是否都会发生？

—未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 劝教是否被文本禁止或限制？

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

是否有明确的改革派活动？

(改革派，比如不是奉劝新保守主义者改教，而是“转化”，或者说改良相关教义，使其变成“正确的阐释”？)

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

本文本是否用于仪式活动？

— 是

Notes: The text serves as a guide for inner alchemical cultivation. It teaches, in Wuzhen pian's term, "the level of attainment, methods, and degrees; the cultivation of tendering and the guidance for restoration"火候法度、溫養指歸. It could be inferred that inner alchemy practitioners would engage the teachings from Wuzhen pian to improve their ritual conducts during their cultivation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 口头背诵吗？

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 口诵经文有没有什么特别的影响？

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 对口诵经文的听众有没有什么特别的影响？

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 关于诵经者？

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 被诵读吗？

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 对文本的读者有什么特别的影响吗？

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 对诵经的听众有没有什么特别的影响？

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 描述仪式活动的性质？

— 请注明: Private meditative practice of inner alchemy

Notes: Inner alchemy (neidan, which literally means internal cinnabar, 内丹) refers to a range of esoteric teachings and practices derived from diverse theories including but not limited to correlative cosmology, laboratory alchemy (also known as outer alchemy, waidan, 外丹) and the teachings of Yijing 易经 (Book of Changes). For a general introduction of the inner alchemy rituals, see Kohn, Livia. *Internal Alchemy: Self, Society, and the Quest for Immortality*. Three Pines Press, 2009.

↳ 是否在大规模的仪式中采用了文本？

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否在小规模的仪式中采用了文本？

— 未知领域

Notes: The text is about inner alchemy, so it possibly did not require a group of people to participate. However, considering that it employs sexual techniques, there could be occasions when the practice requires more than one person to complete.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 仪式多久举行一次？

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

读者群情况：✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否有正信 (orthodoxy) 审查？

— 未知领域

↳ 是否有正行 (orthopraxy) 审查？

— 未知领域

↳ 有同步实践练习吗？
— 未知领域

↳ 仪式中是否使用了麻醉剂？
— 否

↳ 祭祀时是否有其他东西（如食物或饮料等）被食用？
— 否

物品对于文本来说重要吗？
— 未知领域

文本的语境和内容（信仰和实践）。

上下文语境

是否有艺术伴随文本出现？
— 是

↳ 书法？
— 未知领域

↳ 插图？
— 是

Notes: See Danfang baojian zhi tu 丹房寶鑑之圖 (The Illustration of Cinnabar Chamber and Treasure Mirror) in the treatise and related illustrations of tiger, dragon, and cauldron.

↳ 装饰 (illuminations) ？
— 否

有多个文本版本吗？
— 是

Notes: The most influential annotated versions include: 紫陽真人悟真篇註疏：張伯端撰、翁葆光註、戴起宗疏 悟真直指：劉一明 悟真篇正義：元真子 悟真篇闡幽：朱元育 For other versions, see section 3.A.4.c The Wuzhen pian and the Southern School in Schipper, Kristofer, and Franciscus Verellen, eds. The Taoist Canon: A Historical Companion to the Daozang. University of Chicago Press, 2019.

↳ 有多个正确版本吗？
— 是

↳ 如果多个版本都通行，各版本之间是否有什么区别？
— 是

↳ 现有版本的文本的年代？
— 否

↳ 文本内容？
— 是

↳ 文本的仪式目的？

—未知领域

↳ 是否有关于哪个版本是正确的争论？
—是

↳ 在关于文本适当版本的辩论中，权威是如何确立的？
—是

↳ 现存版本的年代？
—是

↳ 文本内容？
—是

Notes: There are debates about the two later added sections.

↳ 文本的仪式目的？
—未知领域

文本是否在为一系列文本的一部分？

—是

Notes: Although being an independent treatise in the Daoist Canon, Wuzhen pian also appears as part of a collection entitled Xiuzhen shishu 修真十書 (Ten Books on the Cultivation of Perfection, DZ 263.26), which was collated in the Yuan dynasty and was also included in the Daoist Canon.

↳ 有经典化的感觉吗？
—是

↳ 权威是如何建立的？
—是

↳ 经典是否可以更改或者添加？
—否

↳ 主要的辩论是否改变了文本在大典中的地位？
—未知领域

↳ 文本是否为系列卷宗的一部分？
—是

↳ 卷宗是如何安排的？
—请注明: Xiuzhen shishu collections ten treatises that are essential to the cultivation of inner alchemy composed during the Song and Yuan dynasties. Wuzhen pian is the fifth treatise in the collection.

如果文本不是明确的经文，它是否属于另一个重要的文学传统？

—否

内容

此文本是否就是或者包含仪式清单、手册、书目、索引、或者词汇表？（选择所有适用选项）

— 仪式手册

是否有复数世系或者单个世系由文本建立？

— 是

Notes: Wuzhen pian was regarded as the foundational scripture of the Southern Lineage of inner alchemy (Nanzong).

↳ 涉及的世系 (lineage) 是否建立了一个权力链？

— 是

Notes: The five patriarchs of the Southern Lineage are: Zhang Boduan 張伯端 (984–1082)–Shi Tai 石泰 (1022–1158)–Xue Daoguang 薛道光 (1078–1191)–Chen Nan 陳楠 (d.1213)–Bai Yuchan 白玉蟾 (1134–1229)

↳ 世系是否由具体的周期或者时间衡量方法来定义？

— 否

↳ 世系是如何建立的？

— 师生关系

文本是否表达了一个正式的法律规定？

— 否

制订专门的宗教历法？

— 否

信仰

文本中是否存在灵与肉的区别？

— 是

Notes: Wuzhen pian takes the essence, pneuma, and spirit as ingredients that are refined in the cauldron, which refers to the physical body. See the song lyric "Cinnabar is the ultimate treasure of the material body. It achieves the myriad of transformations after gaining achievement in cultivation. Further seeking the perfected ancestor of one's nature (spirit). Thus knowing the magical effect of life and death" 丹是色身至寶，煉成變化無窮。更於性上究真宗，決了死生妙用在 the original text.

↳ 精神-心智被设想为具有与其他部分有质的不同的力量或属性？

— 是

↳ 精神-思想被视为非物质，在本体论上与身体不同？

— 否

↳ 其他精神-身体关系？

— 我不知道

↳ 在心灵的概念中：是否存在独特的心理状态或集合体(aggregate)的概念？

— 否

↳ 修行者是否参与关于灵肉二元论的讨论？

— 否

↳ 讨论是否以其他方式进行？
— 否

↳ 修行者是否分别肉体与非肉体的灵魂或者精神？
— 是

↳ 辩论中是否有其他方面或特点？
— 否

↳ 什么是历史上的主流和少数派立场？
— 我不知道

文本中是否表明相信有死后生命？
— 否

Notes: The goal of the cultivation is to escape death and attain immortality. The treatise argues that an attained practitioner would be able to ascend to heaven and live in eternity. It could be interpreted as a form of afterlife imagination.

文本中是否注明相信这个世界有轮回？
— 否

文中是否提到对信徒的尸体进行特殊处理？
— 否

文本是否指出应该在埋葬时出现共同献祭？
— 否

文本是否指明用于埋葬的墓葬品？
— 否

文本中是否存在正式的埋葬？
— 否

文本中是否展现了与葬礼有关的实践？
— 否

文本中是否有超自然生物存在？
— 是

Notes: The treatise mentions that if one learns the essence of the work, he would be able to meet with the Great Supreme Elders of the Three Pure Ones 三清太上翁, who is the highest deities in the tradition. For further explanation of the Three Pure Ones in the Daoist pantheon, see <http://www.chebucto.ns.ca/Philosophy/Taichi/gods.html>

↳ 是否有至上天神存在？
— 是

↳ 至上天神 (supreme high god) 是拟人化的，或用拟人化的术语描述的
— 否

↳ 至上天神 (supreme high god) 是天空神祇

— 是

↳ 至上天神 (supreme high god) 是冥界神 (在地下)

— 否

↳ 至上天神(The supreme high god)与君主融合在一起 (国王=天神)

— 是

Notes: The Daoist pantheon is imagined to have an imperial structure. Although Wuzhen pian does not elaborate on whether the god fuses with a monarch explicitly, it mentions the existence of the highest god and includes expressions such as "Being reborn and becoming deified, having his name inscribed in the immortal register, assuming the position and receiving the title of the perfected being, this is the time when a man of character becomes successful and famous" 脱胎神化，名题仙籍，位就真人，此乃大丈夫功成名遂之时也， which resembles the description of a literatus entering officialdom. In other words, the text implies the existence of the highest deity in the form of a monarch although it does not refer to a specific historical person.

↳ 君主被看成是至上天神的表现或者散发

— 否

↳ 至上天神与精英们是亲属关系

— 是

↳ 至上天神与精英之间有另外的忠诚关系

— 否

↳ 至上天神毋庸置疑是好的

— 是

↳ 至上天神的其他特点

— 请注明: no

↳ 至上天神对这个世界有了解

— 未知领域

↳ 在这个世界是否有蓄意的因果效应

— 未知领域

↳ 这个世界的间接因果效应

— 未知领域

↳ 表现出积极的情绪

— 否

↳ 表现出负面的情绪

— 否

↳ 拥有饥饿感?

— 否

↳ 会被伤害？
— 否

↳ 会被欺骗？
— 否

↳ 会被囚禁？
— 否

↳ 是否允许崇拜至上天神以外的超自然生物？
— 是

↳ 至上天神拥有/表现出一些其他特征
— 请注明: Don't know

↳ 至上天神与生灵沟通
— 否

↳ 文本是否让与至上天神的沟通成为可能？
— 是

Notes: One poem in Wuzhen pian writes: If one understands the meaning of the poem, He can visualize/meet with the Great Supreme Elders of the Three Pure Ones instantly. 若人了得詩中意，立見三清太上翁。

↳ 受众可以直接和神通过文本沟通吗？
— 否

↳ 作为文本的结果，受众可以通过超自然的中介与天神沟通吗？
— 否

↳ 是否存在灵感或灵感知识的概念？
— 是

Notes: The title of the treatise, Wuzhen pian, meaning "Awakening to Truth," connotes the sense of inspiration. It insinuates the truth teachings through poems and expects the learners to "see the branches and awake to the root, discard the false and follow the truth" 見末而悟本，捨妄以從真。

↳ 获得启发的知识是否需要举行仪式？
— 是

Notes: Rituals of inner alchemy are practiced during the process of learning.

↳ 存在哪些关于灵感的概念？例如，千里眼、洞察力、对神圣世界的视野、对神圣的无所不在的机构或全能存在的意识、叹息或超越五官的视野）。
— 是

Notes: A poem in Wuzhen pian visualizes the celestial palaces that one could ascend to after he achieves the inner alchemical cultivation: (I) only anticipate the time when the practice is successful and (I can) pay homage to the northern imperial palace. Wrapped in the shine of the nine rosy clouds, (I) ride on the auspicious Simurgh. 只候功成朝北闕，九霞光裏駕祥鸞。

先前人类灵魂存在

— 否

非人类超自然生灵是存在的

— 否

文本是否证明了一个超自然存在的神系 (pantheon) ?

— 是

Notes: The annotated work of Wuzhen pian, Ziyang zhenren wuzhen pian zhushu 紫陽真人悟真篇註疏, offers supplementary information of the Daoist pantheon implied by the scripture: Among deities and immortals, the earthly immortals detest the life in the mundane world they retreat from the mundane world, in order to return to the three mountains. The heavenly immortals detest the life in the three immortal islands they received the heavenly scriptures in order to return to the grotto-heavens. They ascend to the eight (realms) and then ascend to the Three Pure Ones. 神仙者，以地仙，厭居塵世.....謝絕塵世，以返三山。天仙者，厭居三島.....受天書以返洞天，升於八又升於三清。

↳ 以家庭模式为基础，按亲属关系组织。

— 否

↳ 按等级组织

— 是

↳ 生灵的力量是针对特定领域的

— 否

↳ 神系 (pantheon) 中的其他组织

— 请注明: No

根据文本，人神混合的生灵是否存在？

— 未知领域

是否有一个超自然的存在，在文本中实际存在/作为文本的结果？

— 否

文本是否指导占卜实践？

— 否

超自然监视

文本中是否有超自然监视？

— 否

在文本中，超自然存在是否会施以惩罚

— 否

Notes: It is worth noting that although Wuzhen pian does not emphasize the inner spirits' supervision, there is a consensus in the Daoist tradition that immoral deeds and worldly desires would impede one's cultivation. As for the case of Wuzhen pian, it took the author's voice, instead of internal supernatural power, to dissuade practitioners from conducting harmful or immoral deeds. For example, one poem warns that it is dangerous: (If one) only desires for rank and wealth, and is eager to get notable and glorious, And does not care about his form and countenance getting withered and haggard. 只貪利祿求榮顯，不顧形容暗悴枯。 In other words, if the practitioner does not follow the author's guide, he could never advance in his cultivation. Consequently, he would never be able to visualize the high gods and attain immortality.

在文本中，超自然的生命是否赋予了奖赏？

— 否

救世主义/末世论

文本中是否存在救世主信仰？

— 否

文本中是否存在末世论？

— 否

规范与道德现实主义

一般的社会规范是由文本规定的吗？

— 否

在宗教文本中是否有习俗惯例与道德的区别？

— 否

文本中是否有核心的重要美德主张？

— 否

时间的倡导

圣经是否要求独身主义（完全禁欲）？

— 否

文本是否要求对性活动进行限制（部分禁欲）？

— 否

该文本是否要求阉割？

— 否

文本要求禁食吗？

— 未知领域

Notes: The treatise regards pure fasting as an inferior practice. Meanwhile, it promotes the cultivation using internal elements and discourages consumption. It is not clear if the practice still requires a certain degree of fasting.

文本是否要求放弃食物机会（对渴望的食物的禁忌）？

— 未知领域

该文本是否要求永久的伤疤或痛苦的身体改变？

— 否

文本是否要求痛苦的身体姿势或短暂的痛苦伤口？

— 否

文本是否要求成人献祭？

— 否

文本是否要求儿童献祭？

— 否

该文本是否要求自我献祭（自杀）？

— 否

文本是否要求献祭财产/贵重物品

— 否

文本是否要求牺牲时间（例：参加会议或服务，定期祈祷等）。

— 否

该文本是否需要承担生理风险？

— 否

该文本是否要求接受道德戒律？

— 我不知道

该文本是否要求群体外成员的边缘化

— 否

文本是否要求参与小规模仪式（私人、家庭）？

— 是

Notes: It could be practiced by the practitioner himself. Under certain circumstances, sexual practice is required, and a woman will participate to assist the practice.

↳ 演出的平均间隔时间是多少？

— 未知领域

文本是否要求参加大型仪式？

— 否

文中是否指出团体内部额外的仪式标记

— 否

文本是否使用了拟亲属关系用语？

— 否

文本中是否包括旨在娱乐的元素？

— 否

文本中是否规定了祭品、供品和圣地的维护？

— 否

文本的机构和生产环境

社会与机构

生产文本的宗教团体的社会，最适合被描绘为：

— 其他

Notes: There was no historical account that records specifically the production and transmission of the scripture during the Song dynasty. Daoist temples could have produced and disseminated manuscript copies. Considering that the scripture is not very long, woodblock printed versions could also be circulating during the Song. It is also possible that the Jin and Yuan dynasties' governments took part in reproducing the scripture. Because the text appears in the Ming dynasty Daoist Canon, it is presumable that the government and probably various publishers were involved in the text's reproduction in the late imperial period.

是否有社会的特定因素控制了文本的再生产（reproduction）？

— 其他

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是否有特定的社会元素参与到文本的破坏中？

— 其他

Notes: It is unknown whether the scripture ever faced the risk of destruction in history. However, Kublai Khan (1215–1294) ordered to destroy Daoist scriptures in 1258. It is possible that some Wuzhen pian copies were also affected.

福利

文本中是否规定了制度化的饥荒救济？

— 否

文本中是否规定了制度化的扶贫？

— 否

文本中是否规定了对老弱病残的机构护理？

— 否

其他形式的福利

— 否

教育

是否有正式的教育机构可用于教授该文本？

— 否

根据文本，是否有规定的正式教育机构？

— 否

文本是否对非宗教教育作出规定？

— 否

文本是否限制了宗教专业人士接受的教育？

— 否

文本是否限制了宗教专业人士间的教育？

— 否

根据文本，教育是否有性别差异？

— 否

就这个文本和更大的文本传统而言，教育是否具有性别差异？

— 是

Notes: The targeted readers of Wuzhen pian are men. Although there was a tradition known as female alchemy (nvdan 女丹), it did not appear until the late Ming.

文本中是否规定了教学关系或比例？(即：1:20；1:1)

— 未知领域

文本是否有倡导与教师的具体关系？

— 否

根据文本本身的规定，教育是否有世俗的报偿/好处？

— 否

官僚机构

官僚机构是由这个文本规范的吗？

— 否

公共工程

文本是否详细说明了与公共服务、设施 (public works) 的互动？

— 否

税收

文本是否规定了征税的形式？

— 否

战争

文本是否提到战争？

— 否

食物生产

文本中是否提到粮食生产/发放？

— 否

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